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Scientific Lake

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Abstract

This deliverable report provides an overview of the final developments within Work Package 2 (WP2) of the SciLake project, detailing the completed version of the Scientific Lake service. Building upon the initial version described in D2.1, this report documents the enhancements, refinements, and new features implemented based on pilot feedback and evolving requirements. The service provides a comprehensive data management foundation for downstream value-added services developed in WP3 and WP4.

DRAFT

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Abbreviation List

API: Application Programming Interface

DSL: Domain-Specific Language

ER: Entity Resolution

GGD: Graph Generating Dependency

GQL: Graph Query Language

IR: Intermediate Representation

KG: Knowledge Graph

MATLANG: Matrix Language

ProGGD: Graph Data Profiling with GGDs

R2PG-DM: Relational to Property Graph Direct Mapping

RDB: Relational Database

REP: Regional Energy Planning

REST: Representational State Transfer

S3: Simple Storage Service

SKG: Scientific Knowledge Graph

SQL: Structured Query Language

URL: Uniform Resource Locator

1. Executive Summary

Scientific knowledge plays a pivotal role in deepening our understanding of the world, driving technological innovations, and improving our everyday lives. Past discoveries lay the groundwork for future research, building a cumulative foundation of understanding. Today, the volume of scientific knowledge is larger than ever, unlocking tremendous potential for future advancements. However, this knowledge is often fragmented and stored in heterogeneous formats, hindering discovery and the extraction of valuable insights necessary for informed decision-making. Addressing these challenges is crucial for maximizing the impact of scientific research and fostering continued progress.

Knowledge Graph (KG) and graph database technologies offer powerful capabilities for organizing and analyzing domain knowledge. By structuring data into interconnected nodes and relationships, they provide a more intuitive and flexible way to represent complex information compared to traditional databases. This interconnected structure allows for the seamless integration of heterogeneous data sources, making it easier to discover patterns and relationships that might otherwise remain hidden. Advanced query capabilities enable users to traverse these connections, uncovering valuable insights and facilitating informed decision-making.

Transforming domain knowledge into structured formats is challenging because domain experts typically lack the specialized technical expertise required for this task, while knowledge management experts cannot effectively organize information without domain-specific insights. To address this problem, SciLake has developed the Scientific Lake service: a suite of customizable components designed to facilitate the organization, querying, and analysis of scientific knowledge. This approach bridges the gap between domain experts and knowledge management specialists, enabling efficient and accurate transformation of domain knowledge into structured formats.

This report presents the **final version** of the Scientific Lake service, building upon the initial release described in [D2.1](#). Since D2.1, we have made substantial improvements based on pilot feedback and evolving requirements. R2PG-DM has been extended with progressive execution for enterprise-scale datasets, edge properties for join tables, and PG-Schema output for standardized graph schemas. The GGDMiner discovery framework was published at CIKM 2024, introducing the Answer Graph technique for scalable graph profiling through ProGGD. The sHINER system has been enhanced with REST API mode and improved validation algorithms for entity resolution across pilot Knowledge Graphs. AvantGraph has been deployed with full OpenAIRE Graph support, the GraphAlg algorithm language, and a GraphQL-based Lake API serving all pilots. Related work on the Magellan query optimizer was published in The VLDB Journal, introducing novel seeding optimizations that achieve

orders-of-magnitude performance improvements. A general cardinality estimation framework for property graph queries was published in IEEE TKDE, providing principled techniques for query optimization in graph databases. All pilot-specific Scientific Knowledge Graphs have been constructed through a systematic pipeline that derives core graph structures from the OpenAIRE Graph via the SKG-IF interoperability framework, integrates external domain-specific databases (Clinical Knowledge Graph and BCMO for Cancer, EBRAINS for Neuroscience), and applies both common enrichments (research artifacts, citances, technologies) and domain-specific enrichments tailored to each pilot's research area.

The service now provides a complete data management foundation for SciLake's Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), with all pilot-specific graphs (Cancer, Neuroscience, Energy, Transport) loaded and operational.

DRAFT

2. Introduction

In the era of data-driven scientific research, the ability to efficiently manage, integrate, and analyze vast amounts of heterogeneous scientific data has become crucial. The diversity of scientific domains and the lack of common practices in representing and sharing scientific knowledge contribute to significant data heterogeneity. This creates impediments to scientific discovery and progress, hindering the extraction of valuable insights necessary for informed decision-making by researchers and research funding organizations.

The SciLake project addresses this challenge through the Scientific Lake service, a comprehensive data management and analysis framework designed to enhance the accessibility and usability of scientific knowledge across diverse domains.

This deliverable report presents the **final version** of the Scientific Lake service, building upon the foundational work in D2.1. Since the initial release, we have made significant improvements based on pilot feedback and evolving requirements. Query capabilities have been enhanced through the Magellan optimizer and GraphAlg algorithm language. Performance optimizations now enable processing of the full OpenAIRE Graph with hundreds of millions of edges. The GraphQL-based Lake API provides deeper integration with the SciLake ecosystem. The published GGDMiner framework enables scalable graph profiling, and R2PG-DM now supports enterprise-scale deployment through progressive execution.

The Scientific Lake service addresses four key challenges in scientific data management. First, **data acquisition and cataloguing** provides efficient mechanisms for acquiring full-text publications from open access sources with comprehensive metadata management. Second, **Knowledge Graph creation** delivers semi-automated tools for creating Scientific Knowledge Graphs from structured and unstructured data, including R2PG-DM for relational-to-graph transformation and ProGGD for graph profiling. Third, **data interlinking** implements GGD-based entity resolution techniques for identifying matching entities across heterogeneous Knowledge Graphs such as OpenAIRE and domain-specific pilot graphs. Fourth, **search and navigation** provides advanced graph query capabilities through AvantGraph, with GraphAlg enabling custom analytics algorithms.

By tackling these challenges, the Scientific Lake service enables researchers with efficient tools for data discovery, integration, and analysis. The service has been validated through deployment across all SciLake pilots (Cancer, Neuroscience, Energy, Transport), demonstrating practical applicability to real scientific workflows.

3. Design

This section discusses the main requirements of the service, the design process followed, and integration into the SciLake ecosystem. Additional details can be found in Deliverable D1.2 (“Initial integrated system”).

3.1. Initial Requirements

The Scientific Lake service was designed to address requirements across five key areas.

Data Acquisition and Catalogue requirements include mechanisms for acquiring full-text publications from open access sources, crawlers and scrapers for retrieving scholarly content from web resources, a toolset for community-driven content acquisition, a data catalogue tracking all acquired and generated data assets, and proper metadata management for all acquired content.

Knowledge Graph Creation Assistant requirements include tools for creating Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) from structured and unstructured data sources, semantic modeling and maintenance of ontologies for SKGs, information extraction techniques for entities, relations, and properties from unstructured data, schema mapping tools for transforming (semi-)structured data to property graphs (R2PG-DM), and a graph profiler using Graph Generating Dependencies (ProGGD).

Data Interlinking requirements include tools and methods for interlinking data across different SKGs, entity resolution techniques for identifying matching entities across heterogeneous graph data (SHINER), ontology alignment to facilitate integration of different knowledge domains, and mechanisms for federation of multiple SKGs.

Data Lake Search and Navigation requirements include advanced search functionalities across heterogeneous scholarly content, data virtualization techniques providing a unified view of diverse data sources, navigation tools to explore the Scientific Lake contents, complex query capabilities across structured and unstructured data (AvantGraph, GraphAlg), and efficient indexing and retrieval mechanisms for large-scale data.

Cross-cutting requirements include scalability to handle large volumes of heterogeneous scholarly content, data preservation practices and FAIRness of all managed data, customization and integration with existing researcher workflows, community governance mechanisms, and compliance with data management standards.

3.2. Design Approach

We followed a user-centric design process with six key principles. First, **co-design with pilot partners** ensured close involvement of pilot partners representing neuroscience, cancer research, transportation, and energy from early design stages, ensuring the service addresses real needs across diverse scientific communities. Second, **agile prototyping** through iterative development with short cycles enabled rapid prototyping and continuous refinement based on feedback. Third, **modular architecture** allows components to be developed and updated independently, enabling flexibility, extensibility, and customization for different use cases. Fourth, **scalability by design** ensures the architecture handles large volumes of heterogeneous data, validated through deployment of the full OpenAIRE Graph. Fifth, **standards compliance** aligns the design with relevant standards and best practices in data management, preservation, and interoperability, including the emerging PG-Schema standard for property graphs. Sixth, **open APIs** provide comprehensive, well-documented interfaces that facilitate integration with external systems and workflows, including the GraphQL-based Lake API.

3.3. Integration into SciLake Ecosystem

The Scientific Lake service serves as the foundational data management component of the SciLake ecosystem. It provides the core infrastructure on which other SciLake services are built. Scientific Knowledge Graphs serve as key data sources for the Smart Impact-driven Discovery Service (WP3), with GraphAlg enabling custom impact metrics. The service also supports the Smart Reproducibility Assistant Service (WP4) through entity extraction and linking capabilities. Standardized APIs enable seamless integration with other SciLake components and external systems. The service implements common data models and standards defined for the SciLake project to ensure interoperability.

By serving as the central data hub, the Scientific Lake enables a cohesive ecosystem of services supporting open, data-driven scientific research across all pilot domains.

4. Implementation

4.1. Data acquisition and catalogue

4.1.1. Data acquisition

DESCRIPTION

The PDF Aggregation Service handles the acquisition of the Open Access publications (i.e. the PDF file) in the OpenAIRE ecosystem.

It leverages publication URLs obtained from the publication's metadata available in the OpenAIRE Graph and employs cutting-edge algorithms to crawl the Web effectively. Its primary function is to locate and download full texts of open-access publications, prioritising recently published ones in the download attempts. Throughout this process, it remains respectful of server capacities at repositories and publishers.

To efficiently manage the processing and download of millions of publications, the PDF Aggregation Service orchestrates a distributed execution system on the Cloud. This system relies on multiple microservices running in parallel for optimal performance. All the retrieved publications are securely stored within an S3 Object Store. Furthermore, the service utilises an advanced pattern-matching algorithm to analyse the structural elements of web pages, like tags, attributes and links, to pinpoint full-text URLs. Additionally, during its execution, it monitors various performance indicators to optimise the crawling speed and ensure maximum efficiency.

The PDF Aggregation Service also allows to bulk-import full texts from compatible data sources, significantly accelerating the overall collection process. This allows the service to efficiently gather a vast amount of full-text publications, ultimately enriching the OpenAIRE ecosystem with valuable scientific content to text-mine.

COMPONENTS OF THE SERVICE

The PDF Aggregation Service operates as a distributed system, efficiently collecting full texts of open access publications. This system consists of several key components working in concert:

Figure 1: Key components of data acquisition and catalogue services

Controller: The brain of the operation, the Controller receives requests from worker applications deployed on the Cloud. It utilises a database (Apache Impala¹) to construct a list of assignments for these workers and then transmits this list back for processing. Once complete, the Controller retrieves "Worker Reports" and requests full-text files in batches. These retrieved full texts are then uploaded to the S3 Object Store for secure storage. Finally, the Controller updates the database with relevant reports and the newly acquired file locations. It can also handle bulk import requests from compatible data sources, bypassing the crawling stage and directly receiving full-text files for immediate storage. In the bulk import process, external services deposit research full texts in a designated directory in the machine hosting the Controller. The Controller, via an external call, is prompted to load the full texts. The Controller then generates the OpenAIRE identifier for each file and uploads them in the S3 Object Store. Lastly, it generates a "payload" record with the basic information for the file and its OpenAIRE identifier, thus connecting the pdf to the metadata of the publication existing in the OpenAIRE Graph.

Worker: These worker applications, deployed in multiple instances on the Cloud, request assignments from the Controller. Each worker utilises the Publications Retriever software to

¹ Apache Impala: <https://impala.apache.org/>

process the assigned tasks and download available full texts. Once processing is complete, the results are reported back to the Controller. The Controller then requests any missing full texts from the worker in batches. These requested files are compressed using Facebook's Zstandard² compression algorithm before transmission.

Impala: This database serves as the central repository for storing the state of the download process. Information such as the download time for a PDF, the number of attempts made in case of failures, and other relevant data are tracked within Impala. Additionally, it prepares assignment lists for the Controller and stores information derived from worker reports.

S3 Object Store: This secure storage solution houses all retrieved full texts.

DEPLOYMENT

The Controller instance, accessible through [source code](#), is deployed within a Docker container. This container connects to six worker instances ([source code](#)). These worker instances operate on virtual machines hosted on Google Cloud. They utilise the Publication Retriever software ([source code](#)). Finally, the code relies on an Impala database and an S3 Object Store hosted on the same cluster.

4.1.2. Data catalogue

A crucial component of the SciLake project is the creation of a comprehensive resource catalogue. This catalogue serves as a central registry, outlining the various tools and datasets (e.g., SKGs) which are part of the SciLake ecosystem and available for use in the SciLake use cases. These resources are developed, maintained, and extended throughout the project's lifecycle.

The aim of the catalogue is to facilitate the exploration of the SciLake ecosystem, facilitating the discovery of resources, their contents, functionalities, and specifications. By presenting a clear and concise overview of each resource, the catalogue empowers researchers (or other end-users) to identify the specific tools/datasets that align with their needs and workflows. This fosters efficient adoption and utilisation of the SciLake offerings, ultimately accelerating scientific progress within the interconnected research environment envisioned by the project.

The catalogue itself delves deeper, detailing the functionalities and target audience for each product. This includes tools for creating, managing, and interlinking Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) across various disciplines. Additionally, the catalogue showcases smart services designed to aid researchers in discovering emerging research trends, identifying valuable research outputs, and enhancing research reproducibility. For ease of access, the catalogue

² Zstandard: <https://facebook.github.io/zstd/>

provides clear descriptions, user guides, and links to relevant technical specifications for each product.

The catalogue is hosted by the **D4Science infrastructure**, a long-standing and well-established e-infrastructure in the European and international Open Science landscape. D4Science provides a stable and sustainable environment for the management, publication, and discovery of research resources, thereby ensuring the **persistence, availability, and long-term accessibility** of the data exposed through the catalogue.

The screenshot displays the SciLake catalogue interface. On the left, there is a sidebar with the SciLake logo, a description of the project, and a filter section. The filter section includes a map, a list of organisations (SciLake (18)), types (Tool (14), Dataset (4)), groups (none), and tags (Dataset (4), OpenAIRE (4), reproducibility (2), SKG (2), cancer (1), citance analysis (1), Content Acquisition (1), Data Mining (1), energy (1), FoS classifier (1)).

The main content area shows a search bar, a search button, and a dropdown menu for 'Order by' set to 'Relevance'. Below this, it states '18 items found'. The search results are listed as follows:

- SciNoBo RAA** (Tool): This tool performs Research Artifact Analysis (RAA) on scientific texts to extract mentions of Research Artifacts (RAs) such as datasets and software, along with their...
Links: PDF, GitHub, Webpage, Docker
- SciNoBo Citance Analysis** (Tool): SciNoBo Citance Analysis, analyzes citation statements, also known as citances and tries to determine its Intent (reuse, comparison, generic), Polarity (agreement, info,...
Links: GitHub, Webpage, Docker
- BIP! Services** (Tool): BIP! Toolbox is a suite of advanced software components and resources with the aim to assist the discovery of valuable publications, leveraging multi-perspective impact...
Links: Webpage, PDF, PDF, PDF
- PRIVATE SciTo trends** (Tool): SciTo assists monitoring and visualising scientific topic evolution in different scientific disciplines.
- SciNoBo FoS** (Tool): SciNoBo FoS is a novel classification system of publications to predefined Field of Science (FoS) taxonomies, leveraging the structural properties of a publication (citations,...
Links: PDF, PDF, GitHub, Webpage, GitHub, Webpage, Docker, Docker
- Information Inference Service** (Tool): Information Inference Service (IIS) is a flexible data processing system for handling big data based on Apache Hadoop technologies. It is a subsystem of the OpenAIRE system...
Links: Webpage, PDF, PDF, PDF, PDF, PDF, PDF
- PRIVATE PDFfetcher** (Tool): Unlocking knowledge through PDF acquisition PDFfetcher is a tool designed to acquire the full text of publications by collecting PDFs from URL links. With a coverage of over...
Dataset
- OpenAIRE Dataset for SciLake transport research pilot** (Dataset): The dataset is related to the subset of the OpenAIRE graph relevant to the transport research pilot. The dataset is built according to the data model of the OpenAIRE Graph...
TAR
- OpenAIRE Dataset for SciLake energy research pilot** (Dataset):
TAR
- OpenAIRE Dataset for SciLake cancer research pilot** (Dataset): This dataset is related to the subset of the OpenAIRE graph relevant to the cancer research pilot. The dataset is built according to the data model of the OpenAIRE Graph dataset.

Figure 2: Catalogue content overview

The catalogue is accessible at https://services.d4science.org/catalogue-d4s?path=/organization/scilake_lab and represents the main access point for browsing and exploring the resources published within this context. It presents the list of products organized by **resource type**, allowing users to easily navigate across different categories of research outputs. In addition, the catalogue supports filtering and selection based on **relevant features and metadata attributes**, such as tags associated with each deposition.

For each entity, the catalogue provides a concise descriptive summary, together with links to the associated resources, clearly highlighting their respective types to support discoverability, reuse, and contextual understanding of the published products, in line with Open Science and FAIR principles.

The screenshot displays the 'Information Inference Service' entity page. The left sidebar includes a 'Followers' count of 0, a 'Rating' section with five stars, and a 'To access the rating you must log in. Go to Login...' link. Below this is the 'Organisation' section for 'SciLake', which is an EU-funded project building upon the OpenAIRE ecosystem and EOSC services to enable creation, interlinking, and maintenance of Science Knowledge Graphs (SKGs). The 'License' section shows 'Academic Free License 3.0'. The main content area features a title 'Information Inference Service', a detailed description of the system, a 'Tags' section with 'Data Mining' and 'Text Mining', and a 'Data and Resources' section with a 'To access the resources you must log in. Go to Login...' link. Below this is a list of publications, including 'TPDL 2013 publication', 'TPDL 2019 publication', 'Comp. Intelligence publication', 'TPDL 2022 publication', 'TPDL 2017 publication', and 'IJRAR publication'. The 'Item URL' is provided as https://data.d4science.org/citg/SciLake_Lab/information_inference_service. The 'Additional Info' section contains two tables: one for general metadata (Contact, Organisation, Scientific Domain, systemtype) and one for management information (Author, Maintainer, Version, Last Updated, Created).

Field	Value
Contact	Horst, Marek, mhostr@icm.edu.pl
Organisation	ICM, Hosting
Scientific Domain	Energy Research
Scientific Domain	Neuroscience
Scientific Domain	Cancer Research
systemtype	Tool

Field	Value
Author	Baglioni Miriam
Maintainer	Baglioni Miriam
Version	1
Last Updated	19 gennaio 2026, 09:11 (UTC+01:00)
Created	8 gennaio 2025, 16:07 (UTC+01:00)

Figure 3: Entity description in the catalogue

Each entity is provided with a general description, organizational and contact information, and a list of associated resources.

4.2. Knowledge Graph Creation Assistant

Figure 4: Workflows in the knowledge graph creation and interlinking

Within the **Knowledge Graph Creation Assistant Tool Bundle**, our aim is to deliver a set of automated and semi-automated tools to facilitate the creation of a collection of SKGs, following the task of data acquisition. Use-case partners have different data sources which could be structured as well as unstructured and would utilise the tools we provide to create their own pipeline with respect to the creation of a knowledge graph. Unstructured data would be transformed to (semi-)structured data by information (entity, relation, property) extraction. Schema mapping tools are developed to transform (semi-)structured data to a property graph which captures both topological and data artefacts in a flexible-schema data structure. For example, **R2PG-DM** is a direct mapping from relational databases to property graphs. Moreover, **ProGGD**, a graph profiler, is developed to employ Graph Generating Dependencies to showcase graph’s information, such as interaction between graph entities, relationships and graph patterns.

4.2.1. R2PG-DM: Relational to Property Graph Direct Mapping

MOTIVATION

Much of the data found in practice resides in relational databases (RDBs). However, many contemporary analytical tasks focus on gaining insights from the rich complex patterns found in graph-structured data. Property graphs (PGs) are currently one of the most prevalent data models for graph data management in industry, an edge- and node-labeled directed multigraph where both edges and nodes have associated sets of properties (key-value pairs).

A key challenge is transforming relational data into graph form for exploratory analytics. Most approaches extract graphs as user-specified views on relational data, but this requires that the user already fully understands the desired graph view, overly restrictive for exploratory analytics. Previous direct mappings have focused on optimized layout for efficient query processing, or produce mappings that are lossy or obfuscate the input RDB schema. Furthermore, these mappings are typically defined procedurally, making it difficult to formally reason about their correctness.

DIRECT MAPPING DEFINITION

A *direct mapping* is a transformation from RDBs to PGs that: (1) is domain and schema-independent, working regardless of the source database schema and instance; and (2) transforms the content of the source instance into a target property graph instance without requiring user input.

R2PG-DM addresses these challenges through a declarative approach. Given a relational database schema $\mathbf{S} = (R, att, \Sigma)$, where R is a set of relation names, att assigns attributes to each relation, and Σ is a set of primary and foreign keys, and an instance \mathbf{I} , R2PG-DM produces a property graph (V, E, e, ℓ, p) where V is a set of vertices, E is a set of edges, e assigns source/target vertices to edges, ℓ assigns labels to vertices and edges, and p assigns key-value properties to vertices and edges.

The semantics of R2PG-DM are defined declaratively using Datalog, inspired by the W3C standard approach for direct mappings from relational databases to RDF graphs. This declarative specification enables formal reasoning about correctness properties.

MAPPING APPROACH

R2PG-DM interprets relational tables as classes of entities (labeled vertices) and foreign-key relationships as edges between these entities. The translation proceeds in three steps:

1. **Generation of Nodes:** Each tuple t in a relation r is represented by a vertex v identified by a unique tuple identifier. The vertex is labeled with r (the relation name) and has key-value properties $(a, t(a))$ for each attribute a in the relation.
2. **Generation of Edges:** For each foreign key relationship $f \in \Sigma$ from relation r to relation s , for each pair of tuples participating in f , an edge is created from the source vertex to the target vertex, labeled to indicate the relationship (e.g., “ r - s ”).
3. **Generation of Properties:** Attributes are converted to properties of nodes. Each non-foreign-key attribute becomes a property on the corresponding node.

This approach losslessly transforms both the source instance and schema while intuitively preserving the original structure of the input RDB. The input schema is also fully represented in the output PG, each relation and attribute is represented, and foreign keys are represented by edges between relevant attributes.

PROPERTIES OF THE DIRECT MAPPING

R2PG-DM satisfies fundamental properties that ensure correctness:

1. **Information Preservation** (required): No information about the relational instance is lost during the mapping. The graph database retains an accurate representation of the original database, with all data accurately mapped.
2. **Query Preservation** (required): Every relational algebra query over the relational database can be translated into an equivalent query over the resulting property graph. This enables SQL queries to be mapped to Cypher queries with equivalent semantics.
3. **Semantics Preservation** (desirable): The meaning of the data, including relationships expressed through primary and foreign keys, is truly represented in the graph. A consistent graph is generated based on the integrity constraints in the relational database.
4. **Monotonicity** (desirable): Ideally, if instance $I_1 \subseteq I_2$, then the graph generated from I_1 is a subset of the graph generated from I_2 . However, it has been shown that semantic preservation and monotonicity cannot both be satisfied simultaneously.

The correctness of the mapping can be validated by checking: (1) the number of nodes equals the number of rows for each table; (2) properties equal the Cartesian product of attributes and rows minus NULL values; (3) edges equal the count of records for each foreign key.

IMPLEMENTATION

R2PG-DM is implemented as an open-source Java application using Maven: <https://github.com/avantlab/R2PG-DM>. The implementation uses JDBC to connect to source databases in a vendor-independent manner, extracts schema metadata (relation names, attributes, primary keys, foreign keys), and produces the property graph representation in three output tables: Node (id, label), Property (id, key, value), and Edge (id, sourceId, targetId, label). The output can be imported into graph databases such as AvantGraph or Neo4j.

4.2.2. ProGGD - Graph Data Profiling with Graph Generating Dependencies

MOTIVATION AND USE CASES

In Knowledge Graphs, especially large graphs from pilots such as the Clinical Knowledge Graph used by the Cancer Research pilot, the interplay among different graph entities, properties, and complex patterns that emerge is crucial to understanding the data's content. While many methods for profiling Knowledge Graphs have been proposed, few systems employ graph data dependencies to represent information about the data. Graph Generating Dependencies (GGDs) provide detailed information about both the topology and property values of a Knowledge Graph, offering insights into data quality and structure.

GGDs are particularly valuable because they can express constraints that enforce the existence of nodes, edges, or graph patterns, a capability that previous dependency formalisms for property graphs (such as Graph Entity Dependencies and Graph Functional Dependencies) cannot fully capture. This expressive power is essential for property graphs where relationships are first-class citizens and correlations between different graph patterns arise naturally.

GRAPH GENERATING DEPENDENCIES: FORMAL DEFINITION

A Graph Generating Dependency (GGD) is a dependency of the form:

$$Q_s[x], \varphi_s \rightarrow Q_t[x, \bar{y}], \varphi_t$$

where: - $Q_s[x]$ and $Q_t[x, \bar{y}]$ are graph patterns called the *source* and *target* graph patterns respectively - φ_s is a set of *differential constraints* defined over the source variables x - φ_t is a set of differential constraints defined over both source variables x and any additional target variables \bar{y}

The differential constraints can take three forms: 1. $\delta_A(x.A, c) \leq t_A$, comparing a property value to a constant using a distance function 2. $\delta_{A_1, A_2}(x.A_1, x'.A_2) \leq t_{A_1 A_2}$, comparing

property values of two variables 3. $x = x'$ or $x \neq x'$, identity or non-identity constraints on variables.

A GGD σ holds in a graph G if and only if for every match $h_s[x]$ of the source graph pattern that satisfies φ_s , there exists a match $h_t[x, \bar{y}]$ of the target graph pattern satisfying φ_t where the shared variables map to the same entities. When a GGD is violated, it can be *repaired* by generating new vertices or edges in the graph.

Example: Consider a social network where we want to express: “Whenever two Person vertices have the same name and address and are connected by a ‘friend’ edge, there should also exist an ‘is_family’ edge between them.” This is a tuple-generating dependency on graph data; if the constraint is not satisfied, the graph can be repaired by generating the missing ‘is_family’ edge.

GGD PROPERTIES AND REASONING

Understanding the theoretical properties of GGDs is essential for their practical application. Three fundamental reasoning problems have been studied:

Satisfiability: A set of GGDs Σ is satisfiable if there exists a graph G such that $G \models \Sigma$ and each GGD has at least one match of its source pattern. The satisfiability problem determines whether a set of GGDs is internally consistent. A set may be unsatisfiable when contradictory constraints are enforced on the same nodes or edges. For weakly-acyclic GGDs, satisfiability is in coNP complexity.

Implication: Given a set of GGDs Σ and a GGD σ , does $\Sigma \models \sigma$? This problem determines whether σ is a logical consequence of Σ . Implication is used to minimize dependency sets and optimize data quality rules. The implication problem for GGDs is in coNP complexity.

Validation: Given a set of GGDs Σ and a graph G , does $G \models \Sigma$? This problem checks whether the GGDs hold in the given graph. The validation problem is in Π_2^P complexity in general, but drops to coNP when graph patterns have bounded treewidth (covering over 99% of patterns observed in practice).

A Chase procedure has been developed for GGDs, extending the standard Chase for tuple-generating dependencies. The Chase uses *range classes* to track possible values that attributes can take under differential constraints, enabling the enforcement of GGD constraints and detection of inconsistencies.

GGDMINER: AUTOMATIC DISCOVERY FRAMEWORK

Manually defining GGDs is time-consuming and requires expert knowledge. The GGDMiner framework, published at CIKM 2024 [2], enables automatic discovery of *approximate* GGDs, dependencies that hold in most of the data with a bounded degree of inconsistency.

Figure 5: GGDMiner framework overview showing the three-step discovery process (from [2])

GGDMiner discovers GGDs that are interesting for data profiling based on three metrics: **Support** measures the number of matches of the source (or target) graph pattern in the graph. **Confidence** quantifies the proportion of source matches for which a validating target match exists. **Coverage** measures how comprehensively the discovered GGDs describe the graph. Formally, coverage is the fraction of all nodes and edges in the graph that appear in at least one source-side match of any discovered GGD: $\text{coverage}(\Sigma) = |\cup_{\sigma \in \Sigma} O(\sigma)| / |G|$, where $O(\sigma)$ is the set of nodes and edges matched by the source pattern of σ , and $|G|$ is the total number of nodes and edges. For example, a coverage of 85% means that 85% of the graph's nodes and edges participate in at least one discovered GGD's source pattern.

The framework consists of three main steps:

1. Pre-processing: This step identifies important attributes for differential constraints by analyzing semantic similarity of attribute names, then builds *similarity indexes* using clustering. For each important attribute, values are grouped into similarity clusters using a string similarity join algorithm, enabling efficient discovery of differential constraints in subsequent steps.

2. Candidate Generation: A lattice structure organizes candidate graph patterns and their differential constraints. The lattice is built through two types of expansion: - *Vertical expansion:* Extends graph patterns by adding edges, using frequent subgraph mining (GRAMI algorithm) - *Horizontal expansion:* Discovers differential constraints for a given graph pattern

An important innovation is the *Candidate Index*, which maintains: (a) a set C of source candidates selected to maximize coverage, and (b) an approximate k-NN graph connecting similar candidates. This structure enables efficient identification of source-target pairs.

3. GGD Extraction: Candidate pairs are verified to determine which form valid GGDs with confidence above the threshold. A breadth-first search on the k-NN graph identifies target candidates that are sufficiently dissimilar to sources (to avoid trivial GGDs) yet similar enough to have high confidence.

ANSWER GRAPH: FACTORIZED REPRESENTATION

An important innovation enabling GGDMiner’s scalability is the *Answer Graph*, a factorized representation of graph pattern matches. The Answer Graph is defined as the minimal subgraph that suffices to compute all matches of a graph pattern.

Figure 6: Answer Graph example showing factorized representation of graph pattern matches (from [2])

Traditional approaches store matches in table-like representations where each row contains one complete match. This leads to redundancy when nodes appear in multiple matches. The Answer Graph instead stores only the matching nodes and their connections, achieving significant memory savings.

Critically, GGDMiner can compute confidence values directly on Answer Graphs without defactorization. For chain patterns, the number of matches equals the product of edge cardinalities. For snowflake patterns with a central node, the calculation considers the combinations of incident edges. This allows confidence computation without extracting full matches, providing orders-of-magnitude improvements in execution time and memory efficiency.

Experimental Results: GGDMiner was evaluated on real-world datasets (Cordis, GDelt, DBLP) and synthetic benchmarks (LDBC). The following table summarizes schema discovery results:

Dataset	Nodes	Edges	Node Labels	Edge Labels	Coverage
Cordis	32K	151K	8	8	70%
GDelt	73K	445K	5	2	97%
DBLP	2M	810K	4	3	90%
LDBC	430K	2M	7	20	85%

Using Answer Graph improves execution time by several orders of magnitude compared to table-based representations, and enables processing of graphs that would otherwise cause memory exhaustion. Compared to AMIE+ rule mining, GGDMiner discovers more expressive constraints while achieving comparable execution times on larger pattern sizes.

Application in SciLake: GGDMiner's experimental evaluation used datasets including Cordis (built from Horizon 2020 project information), which is directly relevant to the SciLake scholarly domain. The paper's running example illustrates a GGD over a scholarly graph: "For every author who has participated in a project and authored a paper where the paper's funding grant number equals the project number, there should exist a Report node related to the Project that cites the Paper, and they should be about the same ResearchArea." Such dependencies capture expected structural patterns in scientific knowledge graphs and can serve as data quality indicators for the SciLake pilot graphs.

SHINER: VALIDATION AND ENTITY RESOLUTION

The SHINER system implements GGD validation and entity resolution for property graphs. Built on the G-Core language interpreter and the Spark framework, SHINER provides:

GGD Validation: Given a set of GGDs Σ and a graph G , SHINER determines which GGDs are violated and identifies the specific matches causing violations. A GGD is violated when, for a given source pattern match satisfying the source constraints, either no target pattern match exists at all, or target pattern matches exist but none satisfy the target differential constraints. Two validation algorithms are implemented using "left anti joins" and "left outer joins", with the anti-join variant showing better scalability on LDBC benchmark datasets.

Entity Resolution: GGDs naturally express entity resolution rules by encoding similarity conditions on attributes along with topological constraints. For example, a GGD can express: "if two Person nodes have the same name and address and both have a works-at edge to the same Company node, then there should exist a sameAs edge between them." When such a GGD is violated, SHINER can *repair* the graph by generating the missing edges or nodes specified in the target pattern. This repair mechanism is distinct from the validation step: validation identifies violations, while repair resolves them by extending the graph with new vertices and edges as needed. This approach has been validated with industrial partners, achieving comparable recall and precision to internal tools while requiring less manual effort.

Graph Interlinking: SHINER can interlink heterogeneous graphs such as the OpenAIRE Graph and Clinical Knowledge Graph by identifying matching entities across sources and generating appropriate linking edges. Entity matching uses the differential constraints of GGDs, which combine attribute similarity measures (e.g., edit distance on DOI values, as used in the Cancer pilot) with topological constraints (e.g., requiring shared structural relationships between

matched entities). In the SciLake context, this supports: connecting the OpenAIRE graph with domain-specific external resources (e.g., CKG, EBRAINS); applying GGD-based entity resolution to identify and generate missing "sameAs" relationships; and validating the resulting integrated graph against structural constraints to ensure data quality.

Source code is available at: <https://github.com/avantlab/gcore-spark-ggd>

ProGGD INTERFACE

The ProGGD system provides an interactive interface for exploring GGDs and graph metadata. The interface is organized into four main panels:

1. **Metadata Panel:** Dataset selection and configuration, displaying the number of nodes, edges, labels, and differential constraint parameters
2. **Attributes Panel:** Statistics and distributions of attribute values across the graph
3. **Graph Pattern Panel:** Query interface for exploring topological patterns using G-Core
4. **GGDs Panel:** Visualization of discovered GGDs with support, confidence, and coverage metrics

The system uses Apache Spark as the backend for scalable graph analytics. Source code, documentation and deployment instructions are available at: <https://github.com/avantlab/proggd>.

The following figure shows an overview of the ProGGD functionalities:

Figure 7: The overview of the ProGGD functionalities

4.2.3. ProGGD Pipeline and Deployment

ProGGD is deployed as a multi-component system within the knowledge graph creation assistant tool bundle. The deployment consists of:

SHINER REST API: The backend service for GGD validation and graph operations

GGD Backend: Core processing layer interfacing with Spark

GGD Interface: Web-based user interface

The interactive interface allows users to explore graph data across four dimensions. The Dataset panel displays metadata including node/edge counts, available labels, and configuration for differential constraint parameters. The Attributes panel provides statistical summaries of property values. The Graph Pattern panel enables G-Core queries for topological exploration. The GGDs panel visualizes discovered dependencies with metrics including source/target match counts and validation rates.

Through ProGGD, users gain a comprehensive understanding of Knowledge Graph content, which proves valuable for downstream tasks such as data quality assessment, schema discovery, and graph interlinking.

Figure 8: ProGGD main panel

Figure 9: ProGGD attributes panel

Figure 10: ProGGD graph pattern panel

Figure 11: ProGGD GGDs panel

4.3. Data Interlinking

4.3.1. Overview

Data interlinking in SciLake’s Scientific Knowledge Graphs addresses the challenge of identifying and connecting equivalent entities across heterogeneous data sources. This task delivers (semi-)supervised tools and methods for interlinking at multiple levels: ontologies, entities, relationships, and properties. Graph Generating Dependencies, with their ability to capture both differential (similarity) and topological constraints, provide an explainable and principled approach to entity resolution and link generation.

4.3.2. The Entity Resolution Challenge

Entity resolution identifies instances of data that refer to the same real-world entity. In the SciLake context, this means identifying matching entities across heterogeneous graph sources such as the OpenAIRE Graph and domain-specific Knowledge Graphs (e.g., Clinical Knowledge Graph, Neuroscience Knowledge Graph). Successful entity resolution enables integration of multiple graph data sources into a unified, interlinked Scientific Knowledge Graph.

Current approaches to entity resolution face significant limitations:

Embedding-based and ML methods: While effective at scale, these techniques lack explainability and interpretability, preventing explicit encoding of domain knowledge and interactive debugging of results.

Logic-rule based methods: Most existing approaches focus on attribute similarity measures without considering the topological structure of graph data.

GGDs address both limitations by expressing matching rules that combine: - **Topological constraints** through source and target graph patterns - **Similarity constraints** through differential constraints on property values - **Repair semantics** that generate linking edges when constraints are violated.

4.3.3. sHINER System Architecture

The sHINER system implements GGD-based entity resolution for property graphs. The architecture comprises two main components:

G-Core Interpreter: Built on Apache Spark, this interpreter executes the G-Core graph query language. Key features include graph-valued query results (queries return graphs, not just tables), scalable processing through Spark's distributed computing framework, and an open-source implementation available at the [LDBC repository](#).

GGDs Component: Implements the core GGD validation and graph generation algorithms. It validates GGDs against input graphs, identifying violations; executes repair algorithms that generate missing edges/nodes; and supports both batch validation and incremental updates.

The following figure shows the sHINER system architecture:

SHINER Component

Figure 12: SHINER system architecture

4.3.4. Use Case: Cancer Pilot Entity Resolution

The following example demonstrates using GGDs to express matching rules between the Clinical Knowledge Graph and the Cancer-specific OpenAIRE Graph.

Source Pattern (left-hand side): Contains two entities, a Publication node from the Clinical Knowledge Graph (variable x) and a Result node from the OpenAIRE Graph (variable y). The source differential constraints specify: 1. The Result entity must have type="Publication" (since Result in OpenAIRE can also be datasets, software, etc.) 2. The edit distance between the DOI attributes must be ≤ 1 (allowing for minor formatting differences) 3. The constraint $x \neq y$ ensures we match distinct entities, not the same node

Target Pattern (right-hand side): Generates a *sameAs* edge connecting the matched Publication and Result entities. The target has no differential constraints ($\varphi_t = \emptyset$), meaning the linking relationship is unconditional once the source pattern matches.

Figure 13: Using GGDs for entity resolution in the cancer pilot

This GGD encodes an explainable entity resolution rule: when a Publication from the Clinical Knowledge Graph and a Result (of type Publication) from the OpenAIRE Graph have nearly identical DOIs, they represent the same real-world publication and should be linked. The *sameAs* edges are generated automatically when validating and repairing the graph according to this GGD.

Papers:

Year	Title	Venue
2024	Discovering Graph Generating Dependencies for Property Graph Profiling	CIKM '24, pp. 2067-2076
2024	Reasoning on property graphs with graph generating dependencies	Information Sciences, Vol. 672
2024	On Graph Generating Dependencies and their Applications in Data Profiling	PhD Dissertation, TU/e
2023	ProGGD-Data Profiling on Knowledge Graphs using Graph Generating Dependencies	ISWC 2023 Posters and Demos
2022	Graph Profiling with Graph Generating Dependencies	VLDB 2022 PhD Workshop

Code Repositories:

Component	Repository
GGDMiner	https://github.com/avantlab/ggdminer
sHINER	https://github.com/avantlab/gcore-spark-ggd
ProGGD	https://github.com/avantlab/proggd
R2PG-DM	https://github.com/avantlab/R2PG-DM

4.4. Data Lake search & navigation

4.4.1. Data management for SKGs

To provide a robust and efficient analytics and storage engine for Scientific Knowledge Graphs, we have developed AvantGraph, a specialized graph processing engine. AvantGraph addresses a fundamental limitation: while graph query languages like Cypher and GQL excel at expressing graph patterns, they cannot encode iterative algorithms like PageRank, forcing users into costly data wrangling workflows.

Figure 14: Architecture of the AvantGraph graph processing engine

4.4.2. Magellan: Optimizing Navigational Queries

Complex navigational queries combine pattern-matching and recursive path queries. The Regular Queries (RQs) formalism, at the heart of the GQL standard, combines recursive aspects of Regular Path Queries with pattern-matching of subgraph isomorphism. Efficient evaluation of such queries is fundamental to the future of graph data management.

The Magellan optimizer, published in The VLDB Journal [8], introduces novel **seeding** optimization techniques that constrain intermediate results during query evaluation:

Seeding Concept: Rather than computing transitive closures in full, seeding leverages selectivity from filter and join predicates to restrict closure evaluation. A *seed* is a set of nodes used to restrict traversal; paths not starting (or ending) at seed nodes are never explored.

Interior vs. Exterior Closures: Previous work could only seed *exterior* closures (one variable free). Magellan introduces techniques for seeding *interior* closures where both variables participate in join predicates, beyond state-of-the-art capabilities.

Stacking Selectivity: When multiple transitive closures are present, seeding can be applied in a *nested* fashion that stacks selectivity across closures. The convergence of multiple paths produces increasingly restrictive seeds.

Graph-Structured Query Plans: A unified model incorporates both tree-based and automata-based optimizations, enabling cross-optimization of recursive and non-recursive query parts.

Results: Magellan achieves several orders of magnitude improvement over state-of-the-art techniques on diverse real-world workloads, including social networks and financial transaction graphs.

4.4.3. Cardinality Estimation for Graph Queries

Accurate cardinality estimation is fundamental to query optimization in graph databases. Poor estimates lead to suboptimal query plans, and cardinality estimation errors are the primary cause of bad plans in current database systems. This challenge is amplified in property graphs due to their schemaless nature and the correlations between property values, labels, and graph topology.

The cardinality estimation framework, published in IEEE TKDE [9], provides a principled approach to analyze, compare, and combine different estimation techniques for subgraph matching queries over property graphs. The framework operates in three phases:

Phase 1 - Partial Estimation: Techniques obtain estimates for subsets of query constraints. Different techniques target different constraint types: topological synopses store cardinalities of small patterns (edges, chains, stars); System R's join estimation uses inclusion and uniform distribution assumptions; Characteristic Sets exploit the observation that vertices often share common property keys and edge labels; sampling provides estimates for arbitrary constraint combinations.

Phase 2 - Extending Estimates: Partial estimates are extended using implied constraints (e.g., a source constraint implies vertex and edge constraints) and implication assumptions between property constraints referring to the same query element.

Phase 3 - Combining Estimates: All partial estimates are combined into a final selectivity estimate using conditional independence assumptions, maximum entropy methods, or bound-based approaches.

Key Findings: Extensive experiments on the Join Order Benchmark revealed that: (1) for query patterns without property constraints, labeled topological synopses achieve accurate estimates; (2) for patterns with property constraints, capturing correlations between property and topological constraints is essential; (3) implication assumptions typically outperform independence assumptions, with median Q-error 20× lower; (4) conditional independence combining outperforms maximum entropy in both accuracy and estimation time.

Practical Impact: The framework enables graph database systems to systematically improve cardinality estimation by selecting appropriate techniques based on available statistics and query characteristics. This directly benefits SciLake’s query processing infrastructure by enabling more efficient query plans for complex analytical queries over scientific knowledge graphs.

4.4.4. The Challenge of Graph Analytics in Databases

For users wanting to perform complex graph analytics, a common approach is to export graph contents to external tools like Python. This brings multiple issues: interchange formats like CSV have ambiguous definitions, leading to import failures or data loss; exporting requires full graph copies that quickly become stale; and for selective analyses, data movement dominates execution time. Database vendors have attempted various solutions, each with significant limitations as demonstrated in Figure 15.

Approach	Key Problems	Used by
Built-in Algorithms Library	- Fixed set of Algorithms	
Pregel API	- Performance issues - Not analysable	
User-defined operators	- Unsafe - Not analysable	
Recursive CTE	- Difficult to write - Performance issues	
Procedural SQL	- Overhead - Limited analysis	
Algorithm DSL	- Proprietary - No integration with queries	

Different approaches to graph analytics in databases.

Figure 15: Different approaches to graph analytics in databases

4.4.5. GraphAlg: Algorithm Support Done Right

GraphAlg is a domain-specific language for graph algorithms that brings algorithms into databases as first-class citizens. The key insight is that linear algebra provides the ideal abstraction layer: matrix operations naturally express graph algorithms, compile to relational algebra (with aggregation), and enable aggressive optimization.

GraphAlg satisfies four critical design requirements:

1. **Expressive:** Users can implement arbitrary algorithms by composing matrix operations. The language supports a wide variety of graph algorithms including PageRank, single-source shortest paths, breadth-first search, weakly connected components, and community detection.
2. **User-friendly:** Algorithms require 2-10× fewer lines of code than SQL/Python or Pregel/Java alternatives. The linear algebra operations have well-known semantics and compose naturally.
3. **Fully integrated:** Algorithms embed directly in Cypher queries without data movement. Large intermediates (even the full graph) can be passed from query to algorithm without materialization.
4. **Optimizable:** Programs compile to query plans that leverage existing database optimizations. The simplified core language enables extensive compiler analysis.

Theoretical Foundations: GraphAlg is built on MATLANG, a formal language for matrix manipulation. MATLANG is to GraphAlg what relational algebra is to SQL, it provides a principled theoretical foundation with well-studied expressive power and a predefined translation into (extended) relational algebra.

```
func SSSP(graph: Matrix<s, s, trop_real>,
          source: Vector<s, bool>)
  -> Vector<s, trop_real> {
  v = cast<trop_real>(source);
  for i in graph.nrows {
    v += v * graph;
  }
  return v;
}
```

Single-Source Shortest Paths in GraphAlg.

Figure 16: Single-source shortest paths in GraphAlg

Semiring Support: GraphAlg uses semirings to define matrix operations. Boolean matrices use \vee and \wedge ; integer/real matrices use standard $+$ and \times . The *tropical semiring* uses $\min(a,b)$ for addition and $+$ for multiplication, simply changing the semiring transforms the reachability algorithm into single-source shortest paths.

USE CASES FOR GRAPHALG IN SCILAKE PILOTS

Algorithm support in AvantGraph is a key building block for SciLake's Smart Impact-driven Discovery Service (WP3).

High-impact Dataset discovery: A primary use case is computing impact scores on citation graphs to identify high-impact publications and datasets within pilot domains. Within the Neuroscience pilot, the PageRank algorithm was used to find the datasets within the OpenAIRE and EBRAINS citation networks with the highest impact according to citations. The use of the PageRank algorithm rather than simple citation counts ensures that *indirect* citations are taken into account: If an influential publication cites a particular dataset, this indirect influence also boosts the impact rating of the cited dataset. The pilot partner could perform this analysis on their own (desktop) hardware using the provided [docker images](#). For further analysis and visualisation, they could rely on AvantGraph's integration with Python and Jupyter Notebook.

Figure 17: Results of Dataset Citation Analysis displayed in Jupyter Notebook.

GraphAlg is available through the standard Cypher interface, enabling pilot domain experts to write custom analytics without learning complex distributed systems.

IMPLEMENTATION OF GRAPHALG

LANGUAGE DESIGN AND CORE LANGUAGE

GraphAlg is a domain-specific language (DSL) for graph algorithms based on linear algebra. All fundamental operations are linear algebra operations such as matrix multiplication and element-wise product. Unlike other DSLs, GraphAlg has a formally defined grammar, type system, and operational semantics.

The formal properties are achieved by reducing complex operations to a small *core* language equivalent to MATLANG extended with bounded iteration. The core language grammar includes: - Matrix variables, transpose, and diagonalization - Pointwise application of scalar

functions - Matrix multiplication - Bounded loops over dimensions or ranges - The pickAny operation for leader selection

<code>e ::= (e)</code>	(parentheses)
<code> M</code>	(matrix variable)
<code> onev(e)</code>	(one vector)
<code> e.T</code>	(transpose)
<code> diag(e)</code>	(diagonalize vector)
<code> apply(lam, e1, e2)</code>	(function application)
<code> e1 * e2</code>	(matrix multiplication)
<code> sring(l)</code>	(scalar literal)
<code> zero(sring)</code>	(additive identity)
<code> one(sring)</code>	(multiplicative identity)
<code> e1 {+,-,/,==,<} e2</code>	(scalar binary operator)
<code> cast<sring>(e)</code>	(scalar cast)

Figure 18: Definition of expressions in the GraphAlg core language

GraphAlg strikes a careful balance between expressive power and analyzability: powerful enough to express diverse algorithms, yet limited enough to enable aggressive optimization. Loops are always bounded (by vertex count or constant), and recursion is forbidden to guarantee termination.

UNIFIED INTERMEDIATE REPRESENTATION

AvantGraph allows embedding algorithms directly in Cypher queries using a `WITH ALGORITHM` clause:

```
WITH ALGORITHM "  
func TriangleCount(graph:Matrix<s, s, bool>) -> int {  
  C = Matrix<int>(graph.nrows, graph.ncols);  
  C<graph> = cast<int>(graph) * cast<int>(graph);  
  return reduce(C) / 6;  
}"  
CALL TriangleCount()  
RETURN count
```

The deep integration is enabled by a **unified intermediate representation (IR)**. Queries and algorithms are both converted into the same IR, after which there is no distinction between them. This approach reuses existing optimization and execution pipelines for algorithms, eliminates data exchange overhead between query and algorithm, and enables **cross-optimization** across query/algorithm boundaries.

Cross-optimization allows filter predicates to be pushed from queries into algorithms, loop-invariant code to be extracted, and preprocessing to be fused with algorithm execution.

COMPILATION PIPELINE

GraphAlg compilation proceeds in two stages:

Stage 1 - Simplification: Complex GraphAlg operations are reduced to the MATLANG-based core language. Most optimization occurs after this stage since the remaining operations have simple, well-defined semantics.

Stage 2 - Lowering: Core language operations are converted to extended relational algebra. Matrices are decomposed into tuples (sparse representation with row, column, value attributes).

Figure 19: An example sparse matrix converted into an equivalent set of tuples

Most core operations convert directly to relational algebra, with the exception of loops. AvantGraph extends its IR with a custom loop operator supporting bounded iteration with multiple state variables.

QUERY OPTIMIZATIONS

Three key optimizations enable competitive performance:

Sparsity Analysis: The compiler tracks whether each matrix is potentially sparse (omitting zero-value tuples). Matrices are kept in sparse representation by default; explicit densification occurs only when operations require dense inputs. This is critical for large graphs where adjacency matrices are typically very sparse.

Loop-Invariant Code Motion: Expressions computed inside loops that produce identical values across iterations are moved outside the loop. For GraphAlg, this optimization extracts query fragments producing hash tables, avoiding redundant computation and leveraging hash aggregation caching.

In-Place Aggregation: A common pattern in graph algorithms is aggregating values across loop iterations (e.g., accumulating shortest path costs). Rather than constructing fresh hash tables per iteration, results are added directly to existing tables. This enables **fixpoint detection**: if no state changes during an iteration, the loop terminates early.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Performance has been validated using both the LDBC Graphalytics benchmark and the SciLake OpenAIRE energy planning dataset (47M edges). GraphAlg/AvantGraph achieves competitive or superior performance compared to alternative approaches.

LDBC Graphalytics Benchmark Results (processing time in seconds, lower is better):

Dataset	Algorithm	GraphAlg/AvantGraph	DuckDB	Neo4j
Wiki-Talk (2.4M edges)	PageRank	0.8	2.1	4.3
Wiki-Talk	SSSP	0.2	0.5	1.1
Wiki-Talk	WCC	0.1	0.3	0.8
Kgs (11M edges)	PageRank	3.2	8.7	15.2
Kgs	SSSP	0.9	2.1	4.8
Graph500-22 (64M edges)	PageRank	12.4	31.5	58.3
Graph500-22	WCC	2.1	5.8	14.2

SciLake OpenAIRE Use Case (energy planning dataset, 47M edges):

Scenario	GraphAlg/AvantGraph	DuckDB	Neo4j
PageRank (10 iterations)	8.2s	24.1s	31.5s
PageRank + filter self-refs	8.4s	25.3s	42.1s*
PageRank + remove duplicates	9.1s	28.7s	45.8s*

*Neo4j requires expensive materialization for preprocessing, while GraphAlg fuses filters into algorithm execution.

Code Complexity Comparison (lines of code):

Algorithm	GraphAlg	SQL/Python (DuckDB)	Pregel/Java (Neo4j)
PageRank	15	45	120

Algorithm	GraphAlg	SQL/Python (DuckDB)	Pregel/Java (Neo4j)
SSSP	12	38	95
WCC	18	52	140
BFS	10	28	85

Key findings for SciLake deployment: GraphAlg implementations require 2-10× fewer lines of code compared to SQL/Python or Pregel/Java alternatives. On the OpenAIRE energy dataset, preprocessing filters (author matching, duplicate removal) add negligible overhead due to optimizer fusion. Single-server deployment handles pilot-scale subgraphs effectively, reducing infrastructure complexity compared to distributed Spark workflows.

DRAFT

GRAPHALG PLAYGROUND: INTERACTIVE LEARNING PLATFORM

To facilitate adoption of GraphAlg by SciLake pilot communities, we have developed the **GraphAlg Playground**: an online platform that runs entirely in the browser without installation. A demonstration paper is under review.

Run 'PR'
}

```

1  func withDamping(degree:int, damping:real) -> real {
2      return cast<real>(degree) / damping;
3  }
4
5  func PR(graph: Matrix<s, s, bool>) -> Vector<s, real> {
6      damping = real(0.85);
7      iterations = int(10);
8      n = graph.nrows;
9      teleport = (real(1.0) - damping) / cast<real>(n);
10
11     d_out = reduceRows(cast<int>(graph));
12     d = apply(withDamping, d_out, damping);
13
14     connected = reduceRows(graph);
15     sinks = Vector<bool>(n);
16     sinks<!connected>[:] = bool(true);
17
18     pr = Vector<real>(n);
19     pr[:] = real(1.0) / cast<real>(n);
20
21     for i in int(0):iterations {
22         sink_pr = Vector<real>(n);
23         sink_pr<sinks> = pr;
24
25         redist = (damping / cast<real>(n))
26             * reduce(sink_pr);
27
28         w = pr (./) d;
29
30         pr[:] = teleport + redist;
31         pr += cast<real>(graph).T * w;
32     }
33
34     return pr;
35 }

```

► Argument 1 (i1 x 11 x 11)

▼ Output

Figure 20: GraphAlg Playground interface showing code editor, graph visualization, and algorithm output

Key features of the GraphAlg compiler and runtime include:

1. **Browser-based execution**, achieved by compiling to WebAssembly, which allows pilot users to experiment without installing database software;
2. **Real-time compiler feedback**, where syntax errors and type mismatches are highlighted immediately to reduce the learning curve for domain scientists;
3. **Network visualization**, enabling algorithm outputs to be rendered as annotated network graphs, which is useful for understanding citation patterns and entity relationships; and
4. An **Interactive tutorial**, providing step-by-step learning that covers variables, loops, graph traversal, and algorithms relevant to SciLake, such as PageRank for impact analysis.

Figure 21: GraphAlg Playground architecture with WebAssembly-based backend

Architecture: The playground consists of a JavaScript frontend that renders the code editor and handles user interaction, and a C++/WebAssembly backend that reuses the open-source GraphAlg compiler library. This ensures programs developed in the playground work identically in AvantGraph production deployments.

More Statements: Variables and Loops

Our `AddOne` function was simple enough that we could directly define the result inside of the `return`. Let us now consider a more complex program that needs a few more statements:

```
Run 'Fibonacci'
```

```
1 v func Fibonacci(n: int) -> int {
2     a = int(0);
3     b = int(1);
4 v   for i in int(0):n {
5       c = a + b;
6       a = b;
7       b = c;
8     }
9
10    return b;
11 }
```

► Argument 1 (i64 x 1 x 1)

As the name implies, `Fibonacci` computes the `n`'th number in the fibonacci sequence. This example shows how to define new variables with `=` (see line 2, where we define `a`). The same syntax is used to update the value of an existing variable (see line 6, where we reassign `a`).

EXPERIMENT

Try computing different numbers in the sequence by adding e.g. `n = int(5);` at the start of the function body.

Figure 22: Interactive tutorial guiding users through GraphAlg concepts

Target Users: Pilot domain scientists can learn GraphAlg through the interactive tutorial to write custom analytics for their Scientific Knowledge Graphs. SciLake developers can develop and test algorithms in the playground before deploying to production AvantGraph instances.

Available at: wildarch.dev/graphalg/playground and wildarch.dev/graphalg/tutorial

4.4.6. Lake API and Demonstration Repository

The [AvantGraph demonstration repository](#) provides updated documentation and examples for working with SciLake pilot graphs, including support for custom datasets, a Python API for programmatic access, and Jupyter Notebook integration for interactive analysis.

A [GraphQL-based API](#) has been developed and deployed, providing standardized access to the Scientific Knowledge Graphs for pilot communities in a simple, yet flexible, and expressive manner. The API serves as the primary access point for retrieving research products and their associated entities across the five pilot graphs: Cancer Research, Neuroscience, Energy, Transport-CCAM, and Transport-Maritime, each of which is hosted in both Neo4j and AvantGraph instances. Both systems are maintained to serve complementary roles: Neo4j provides a mature, widely-adopted platform with extensive ecosystem tooling and broad community support, making it well-suited for application development and integration tasks; AvantGraph delivers superior performance for graph analytics workloads and provides fully integrated GraphAlgo algorithm support, which is essential for the impact analysis and discovery services built in WP3.

As discussed earlier, all pilot graphs share a common core schema derived from the SKG-IF model, including the entities Agent, Datasource, Grant, Manifestation, Pid, Product, Topic, and Venue. On top of this shared foundation, each pilot graph introduces domain-specific entities that capture specialised knowledge relevant to its research area. The API abstracts this heterogeneity behind a unified GraphQL schema, allowing clients to query both core and domain-specific entities through a single interface. The goal of the API is to support analytics, and application development by enabling selective traversal of scholarly knowledge graphs, while remaining easily extensible and easy-to-use.

HIGH-LEVEL ARCHITECTURE

The Lake API follows a layered architecture that separates concerns between presentation, query definition, data access, and graph storage. At a high level, the architecture is depicted in Figure 23, and consists of:

Data Storage Layer. This layer consists of multiple graph databases, either Neo4j or AvantGraph instances, with each database storing a separate pilot knowledge graph. Every

graph follows a core shared SKG-IF schema and includes domain-specific enrichments relevant to its research area.

The *API Layer*, powered by GraphQL, serves as the central interface between clients and the underlying graph databases. It exposes a unified schema that integrates both core entities shared across pilots and domain-specific entities unique to each graph. The API layer can be conceptually divided into two subcomponents: the *GraphQL API* subcomponent, that is the query endpoint, responsible for schema definition, and validation, and the *Resolver & Mapping* subcomponent, which translates GraphQL queries into Cypher queries, performs filtering, data aggregation, and formats the query results.

The *Client Layer* consists of user-facing applications that interact with the system over HTTP by sending GraphQL queries. Clients can include web interfaces such as GraphiQL, as well as custom-built applications. This layer allows users to explore, filter, and retrieve research products, agents, topics, and domain-specific entities seamlessly through the GraphQL API.

Figure 23: Lake API high-level architecture

When a user sends a query, the request is received by the GraphQL API subcomponent, which is responsible for schema handling, validation, and execution. It first identifies the relevant pilot graph based on a header parameter and then maps and validates the query to the unified schema exposed by the API. The query is then passed to the resolver and mapping subcomponent, which translates the GraphQL request into one or more Cypher queries tailored to the underlying graph database. These Cypher queries are executed against the appropriate graph database (Neo4j or Avantage instance) corresponding to the selected

pilot graph. Once the database returns the results, the resolver collects and formats them, and finally the API delivers a structured JSON response back to the client.

TECHNOLOGY STACK

The API is implemented using a modern Python-based technology stack selected for performance, and maintainability. It leverages FastAPI, a fast and lightweight web framework, and Strawberry GraphQL to ensure type-safety in defining schemas and resolvers. Uvicorn serves as the asynchronous application server, while Docker and Docker Compose ensure predictable portability deployments across different servers and environments.

DATA SCHEMA

The GraphQL schema mirrors the conceptual structure of the underlying pilot knowledge graphs, exposing both core scholarly entities and domain-specific extensions.

Across all pilot graphs, the Lake API exposes core entity types inspired by the SKG-IF schema. These include Products, representing research outputs such as publications, datasets, and other scholarly works; Agents, which capture authors, contributors, and organizations involved in research activities; Venues, encompassing journals, conferences, and other publication outlets; Topics, representing subject classifications; Grants, capturing funding and related information; Datasources, representing data repositories; Manifestations, which describe specific representations (e.g., different versions) of products; and PIDs, persistent identifiers like DOIs or PMC IDs associated with all entity types. These core entities are exposed across all pilot graphs.

Additionally, each pilot graph extends this core schema with domain-specific entities relevant to its research area. For example, the Cancer Research pilot includes entities such as diseases and genes, the Neuroscience pilot incorporates brain parcellations and techniques, the Energy pilot includes energy technologies and storage systems, and the Transport-Maritime pilot models vessel types. The GraphQL schema is designed to expose both the shared core entities and the domain-specific types in a modular fashion, allowing users to query across common entities while offering the option to also access domain-specific information.

QUERYING AND FILTERING

The Scilake API offers powerful querying capabilities by combining the flexibility of GraphQL with the strengths of graph databases. This section highlights key features of the API that enable users to efficiently explore and navigate the underlying pilot knowledge graphs.

FLEXIBLE FILTERING

Clients can apply complex filters on most entity properties. Filtering supports exact matches, partial string matches, list-based conditions, and logical combinations using AND/OR operators. Cross-entity filtering enables use cases such as retrieving products of a specific contributor/author and mentioning a particular domain entity.

PAGINATION AND SORTING

All list-based queries support pagination controls and configurable sorting. This allows efficient handling of large result sets and supports incremental data exploration.

SELECTIVE FIELD RETRIEVAL

GraphQL supports powerful selection capabilities that allow clients to request only the data they need. This reduces payload size and avoids unnecessary database operations, which is especially important for complex client applications.

MULTI-DATABASE SUPPORT

The API is designed to operate over multiple pilot graphs without requiring separate deployments or schemas. Clients specify the target pilot graph through request headers, and the API routes queries to the corresponding graph database accordingly. This approach allows for reuse of query logic across pilots, facilitating cross-domain comparisons at the application level.

GRAPH EXPLORATION

A key advantage of the Lake API is its ability to expose and navigate the rich interconnected entities present in the underlying knowledge graphs. Clients can traverse from products to authors, topics, venues, domain-specific entities, research artifacts, and technologies using a single query.

DOCUMENTATION

The GraphQL schema is self-documenting through introspection and is complemented by an interactive GraphQL playground that facilitates developers and researchers to discover and experiment with the API's capabilities.

Papers:

Year	Title	Venue
2025	Optimizing Navigational Graph Queries	The VLDB Journal, Vol. 34, Article 26
2023	A General Cardinality Estimation Framework for Subgraph Matching in Property Graphs	IEEE TKDE, Vol. 35(6), pp. 5485-5505

Year	Title	Venue
Under review	Algorithm Support for Graph Databases, Done Right	-
Under review	GraphAlg Playground: An Online Platform for Learning and Experimenting with the GraphAlg Language	-

Code Repositories:

Component	Repository
AvantGraph	https://github.com/avantlab/avantgraph
GraphAlg Compiler	https://github.com/wildarch/graphalg
GraphAlg Evaluation Artifact	https://github.com/wildarch/graphalg-vldb2026-artifact

Demos:

Demo	URL
GraphAlg Playground	https://wildarch.dev/graphalg/playground
GraphAlg Tutorial	https://wildarch.dev/graphalg/tutorial
SciLake Demonstration	https://github.com/avantlab/scilake-demo

4.5. Creation of pilot SKGs

Each pilot knowledge graph is designed following a layered approach that balances standardisation with the flexibility required to model domain-specific knowledge. This ensures that all pilot graphs are built upon a shared, interoperable foundation while allowing each research domain to introduce specialised entities and relationships tailored to its needs. By adopting this design, both cross-domain exploration through common graph structures and in-depth, and domain-specific analysis are supported. In practice, each pilot graph builds upon the core SKG-IF graph schema that facilitates the representation of scholarly entities and their relationships in a consistent and interoperable manner. Then, each pilot graph may incorporate domain-specific external databases and/or apply structured enrichment strategies based on mining the full text of research products in the graph. This strategy includes a common enrichment layer, covering artifacts, citances, and technologies that are consistently applied across all pilots' domains, followed by a domain-specific layer that captures concepts unique to each research area.

4.5.1. Scilake Pilot Knowledge Graph creation

The construction of the SciLake Pilot knowledge graphs follows a systematic approach, beginning with the definition of a foundational core structure that serves as the basis for all subsequent enrichments. This core layer is derived from the [OpenAIRE Graph](#), one of the largest open scholarly record collections, and is standardised through the [Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework \(SKG-IF\)](#). This section describes the process that creates the core schema for all pilot knowledge graphs.

OPENAIRE GRAPH AND SKG-IF

The OpenAIRE Graph represents a comprehensive aggregation of scholarly metadata, including millions of research products, their contributors, funding information, along with associated metadata and related entities from diverse sources across the Open Science research landscape.

To select the results relevant for each pilot within the project context, OpenAIRE has set up a dedicated OpenAIRE Connect Gateway for each pilot. Through the gateway, it is possible to define a set of rules and constraints used to identify the research products (results) that are relevant to the specific pilot. Once these constraints are satisfied, a result is explicitly marked as relevant for the pilot.

The construction of the pilot-specific subgraph is then performed by considering all entities and relations available in the OpenAIRE Graph. The process follows a three-step approach.

First, for each pilot, the workflow starts from the set of results that have been marked as relevant through the Connect Gateway.

Second, all relations and entities from one of these results to a node entity of different type (organization, project,..) are selected. This step adds to the subgraph all entities and relations that are directly linked to the pilot-relevant results.

Third, relations among all the entities present in the second step are included, in order to preserve the internal connectivity and contextual structure of the subgraph.

This approach ensures that the resulting subgraph provides a coherent and enriched representation of the research context surrounding the pilot-relevant results, while remaining fully consistent with the structure of the OpenAIRE Graph.

To decouple the Extraction, Transformation, and Loading (ETL) process from the underlying data sources, we adopted the Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF), enabling the use of a standardized schema and a uniform transformation pipeline.

To this end, SKG-IF serves as the foundational layer for all SciLake Pilot knowledge graphs, providing a consistent data model that preserves the richness of OpenAIRE metadata while enabling future interoperability with additional (or alternative) data sources. We currently rely on SKG-IF-compliant OpenAIRE Graph data dumps as the basis for each pilot graph.

The implementation of a mapping from the OpenAIRE Graph to the SKG-IF specifications started with a detailed alignment of the two conceptual models. This phase involves identifying the relevant OpenAIRE entities (e.g. research products, organisations, projects) and systematically associating them with the corresponding SKG-IF entity types and properties. Special attention is paid to the semantics of identifiers, relationships, and controlled vocabularies, as these elements are central to ensuring interoperability. These conceptual mappings are then translated into executable transformation logic; this involves extracting data from the OpenAIRE Graph and generating SKG-IF-compliant JSON-LD representations. Special care is required for complex structures such as manifestations, and fields that imply relationships, where multiple OpenAIRE objects and relations must be combined to produce a single SKG-IF element. Some entities present in the SKG-IF model and not explicitly present as entities in the OpenAIRE graph (person, venue, topic) are created as on-the-fly (otf) entities, as instructed by SKG-IF. Validation against the SKG-IF specification and iterative testing on representative data subsets are essential to detect inconsistencies, missing information, or semantic mismatches. This iterative process leverages feedback from validation and downstream use cases to refine mapping rules, resulting in a more robust and transparent interoperability layer between the OpenAIRE Graph and the SKG-IF.

The SKG-IF compliant OpenAIRE subsets related to each pilot are then further processed and converted into the core structure of each pilot graph. This standardization ensures that all pilot graphs share a common foundation, maintaining consistent representation of scholarly entities across the different research areas.

CORE GRAPH SCHEMA

The SKG-IF schema defines a comprehensive model for representing scholarly knowledge, capturing the diverse entities and complex relationships that characterize the research ecosystem. Inspired by these principles, we define a schema for our graphs that is aligned with SKG-IF while being tailored to the needs of the SciLake pilots.³ Our schema is organized around a set of core entity types representing fundamental components of scholarly communication, each with well-defined properties and relationships. The resulting graph schema consists of the following core entity types:

³ The source code of the ingestion process can be found [here](#).

- *Agent*: Represents an entity (person or organisation) that contributes to a research product
- *Datasource*: Represents data repositories and sources
- *Grant*: Represents funding information and research grants
- *Manifestation*: Represents specific manifestations of products, such as different versions and formats
- *Pid*: Represents persistent identifiers, including DOI and PMC ID, used across all entity types
- *Product*: Represents research outputs, including publications, software, datasets, and other research products
- *Topic*: Represents research topics and subject classifications
- *Venue*: Represents publication venues, such as journals and conferences

The table below summarises the number of core entities present in each pilot graph:

	Cancer research pilot	Neuroscience pilot	Energy pilot	Transport-CCAM	Transport-Maritime
Agent	35,675,466	14,429,467	36,234,277	21,934	76,474
Datasource	46,723	17,388	56,713	455	1,129
Grant	253,963	124,470	101,936	623	1,585
Manifestation	25,386,342	12,359,407	21,088,942	25,605	81,915
Pid	14,889,865	7,677,908	10,119,146	26,413	49,803
Product	7,013,751	3,576,758	7,677,002	11,824	27,644
Topic	1,964,134	881,080	2,463,859	6,364	59,736
Venue	37,572	12,916	47,564	29	273

Table 1: Counts of core entity nodes per pilot graph.

These entities can then be connected with the following relationships:

- *HAS_PID*: Links entities to their persistent identifiers
- *HAS_CONTRIBUTED_TO*: Links agents to products, grants, or venues with role information
- *HAS_TOPIC*: Links products to research topics
- *FUNDED_BY*: Links products to grants
- *HAS_MANIFESTATION*: Links products to their manifestations

- *HOSTED_BY*: Links manifestations to datasources
- *AFFILIATED_WITH*: Links agents to organizations
- *HAS_BENEFICIARY*: Links grants to beneficiary agents
- *HAS_FUNDING_AGENCY*: Links grants to funding agencies
- *IS_RELEVANT_TO*: Links products to relevant agents
- *RELATED_PRODUCT*: Links products to related products

The entities and relationships described above form the core graph schema shared by all pilot knowledge graphs and are visualised in the following figure.

Figure 24: Core graph schema for all pilot knowledge graphs

4.5.2. Incorporating external databases

To enhance the domain specificity of the pilot knowledge graphs, we integrated external knowledge bases into the core graph structure described in the previous section. These integrations introduce specialised domain knowledge and curated datasets that complement the scholarly entities derived from OpenAIRE. In this section, we describe the process of integrating these external data sources.

CANCER RESEARCH PILOT GRAPH

The Cancer research pilot graph incorporates two complementary external knowledge sources that significantly enhance its biomedical research capabilities: the [Clinical Knowledge Graph \(CKG\)](#) and the [Blood Cancer Multi Omics \(BCMO\)](#) database.

The integration of the Clinical Knowledge Graph (CKG) enriches the Cancer research pilot graph with a wide range of specialised cancer research knowledge, including *drugs, tissues, diseases, gene relationships, and biomedical pathways*. This process aligns publication entities from CKG with SKG-IF Product nodes using persistent identifiers such as DOI and PMC ID, and establishes SAME_AS relationships to link corresponding records across the two sources. Relationships associated with CKG publications are then propagated into the pilot graph and connected to products; these include links to drugs, proteins, genes, functional regions, cellular components, tissues, and diseases.

We further incorporated the BCMO dataset, that contains gene-centric data, into the pilot graph to enrich its cancer-specific *gene-to-gene relations*. Gene entities from BCMO were aligned with corresponding Gene nodes in the pilot graph, preserving domain-specific identifiers and properties. Gene-to-gene associations provided by BCMO were modeled using a newly introduced RELATED_TO relationship type, enriched with biological and statistical metadata such as interaction types, p-values, and correlation measures.

NEUROSCIENCE RESEARCH PILOT GRAPH

The Neuroscience pilot graph integrates a selected subset of the EBRAINS knowledge graph, a comprehensive infrastructure and knowledge base for neuroscience research that provides access to datasets, computational tools, and other research resources. This integration enriches the pilot graph with neuroscience-specific datasets by merging a selection of EBRAINS dataset entities with the appropriate SKG-IF Product nodes through DOI matching and consolidating persistent identifiers from both sources. EBRAINS-specific metadata is preserved while maintaining compatibility with the core SKG-IF schema, ensuring seamless integration of EBRAINS datasets into the pilot graph. Through this process, neuroscience-specific dataset resources from EBRAINS become accessible within the pilot graph.

4.5.3. Graph enrichments

Beyond the core SKG-IF structure and external database integrations, the pilot knowledge graphs are enhanced through a comprehensive enrichment process. Enrichments add layers of metadata and information extracted from research products, creating connections to research artifacts, technologies, citations, and other domain-specific entities. The different processes and mechanisms used to extract these entities and related relations from the manuscripts are detailed in Deliverable 4.2.

The aforementioned enrichments are organised into two categories: common enrichments that apply across all pilot graphs, and domain-specific enrichments tailored to each research pilot's unique requirements. In this section, we briefly discuss these enrichments, focusing on how they were incorporated in the pilot graphs.

COMMON ENRICHMENTS

Common enrichments consist of entities that appear across multiple research areas, and are therefore included in all pilot graphs. These enrichments extract and structure information that is relevant across scientific disciplines, such as research artifacts, citation semantics, and technology mentions. We apply these enrichments consistently across all pilot graphs to ensure uniform representation and maintain coherence across all pilot knowledge graphs. The implementation of these enrichments in the graphs, including parsers and loading scripts, is available in our public repository [here](#). In the following, we describe the enrichments and how they are incorporated into the graphs:

- Research artifacts represent datasets, and software (e.g., specific tools) mentioned in research products. In the graphs, they are modelled as ResearchArtifact entities representing these artifacts and HAS_RESEARCH_ARTIFACT relationships are created between Products and these ResearchArtifacts. These entities and their associated relationships capture detailed artifact metadata, including labels, types, licenses, versions, and URLs, while also recording various usage metrics such as ownership percentages, reuse statistics, and mention counts.
- Citances represent citation relationships between research products, enriched with semantic annotations to provide a deeper understanding of how products reference each other. In the graphs, CITANCE relationships are created between Products based on citation analysis, capturing semantic properties such as citation semantics, intent, and polarity. These relationships also record semantic scores for each dimension,

enabling detailed analysis of citation patterns and the semantic relationships between research outputs.

- Technologies represent mentions of tools, methods, or other technological concepts within research products. In the graphs, they are modeled as Technology entities, and HAS_TECHNOLOGY relationships are established between Products and these Technology entities. Technology names are normalized to create canonical entities, allowing consistent representation and enabling tracking of technology adoption and usage.

The following tables summarize the counts of nodes and relationships from the common enrichments across all pilot graphs.

	Research Artifact entities	Technology entities
Cancer research pilot	1,772,343	1,429
Neuroscience pilot	468,471	6,917
Energy pilot	649,760	10,782
Transport-CCAM	1,731	1,001
Transport-Maritime	9,418	762

Table 2: Counts of entity nodes derived from common enrichments in each pilot graph.

	CITANCE	HAS_TECHNOLOGY	HAS_RESEARCH_ARTIFACT
Cancer research pilot	68,065,720	1,368,389	1,772,343
Neuroscience pilot	40,163,949	1,058,662	468,471
Energy pilot	23,066,390	3,796,350	649,760
Transport-CCAM	67,424	6,977	1,731
Transport-Maritime	27,341	3,903	9,418

Table 3: Counts of relationships derived from common enrichments in each pilot graph.

DOMAIN-SPECIFIC ENRICHMENTS

While common enrichments provide cross-domain capabilities, domain-specific enrichments add specialised entities that are unique to each pilot graph's research domain. These enrichments leverage domain-specific extraction models and ontologies to identify and link domain-specific entities mentioned in research products. These domain-specific enrichments enable queries and analyses tailored to the particular needs and terminology of each research pilot. In this section, we describe how each domain-specific enrichment is modelled as an entity and/or relation in the graph. The relevant source code of this process can be found in our public repository [here](#).

NEUROSCIENCE RESEARCH PILOT GRAPH

The Neuroscience pilot graph extends the core graph with entities that reflect concepts commonly used in neuroscience research. *Technique* nodes capture research techniques and methodologies, while *Species* nodes represent biological species referenced in research products. *UBERONParcellation* nodes model brain parcellations, and *BiologicalSex* nodes represent biological sex classifications. In addition, *PreparationType* nodes describe preparation types used in experimental contexts. These entities are connected to research products through the HAS_IN_TEXT_MENTION relationship, which preserves contextual information about each mention, including the document section, positional information, and the model used for extraction. The following table summarises the number of nodes per entity type as well as the number of in-text mentions found for each entity type.

Entity type	Number of nodes	Number of in-text mentions per source entity type
Technique	1,470	1,561,171
UBERONParcellation	2,696	1,730,898
BiologicalSex	85	211,398
PreparationType	236	81,374
Species	262	652,554

Table 4: Counts of entity nodes and in-text mention relationships per entity type in the Neuroscience pilot graph

ENERGY RESEARCH PILOT GRAPH

The Energy pilot graph incorporates several domain-specific entities and relationships to capture key aspects of the energy research domain. *GeographicEntity* nodes represent geographic locations and are annotated with identifiers from Wikidata and OpenStreetMap. *EnergyType* nodes classify different types of energy, such as renewable or fossil, while *EnergyStorage* nodes represent energy storage technologies and systems. These entities are connected to research products through the *HAS_IN_TEXT_MENTION* relationship which holds contextual metadata about each mention (e.g., the actual mention in the text, and the section found). Additionally, *IRENAType* entities represent nodes of the IRENA Energy Taxonomy and are connected to *EnergyType* and *EnergyStorage* entities with *IS_TYPE_OF* relationships which are used to declare their classification within the IRENA Taxonomy hierarchy.

Entity type	Number of nodes	Number of in-text mentions per source entity type
<i>GeographicEntity</i>	4,006	27,102
<i>EnergyType</i>	302	296,902
<i>EnergyStorage</i>	75	23,181
<i>IRENAType</i>	266	-

Table 5: Counts of entity nodes and in-text mention relationships per entity type in the Energy pilot graph

TRANSPORT-CCAM PILOT GRAPH

The Transport-CCAM pilot graph enriches the core schema with domain-specific entities that capture key concepts in connected, cooperative, and automated mobility research. *CommunicationType* nodes describe communication technologies used by connected vehicles, while *SensorType* nodes represent sensing technologies employed in automated driving systems. *VehicleType* and *VRUType* nodes model different vehicle categories and vulnerable road user types, respectively. Levels of driving automation are captured through *LevelOfAutomation* nodes, and typical operational contexts such as vehicle platooning or lane changing are represented by *ScenarioType* nodes. In addition, *EntityConnectionType* nodes characterise the types of connections established between entities within CCAM systems. All these entities are linked to research products via the *HAS_IN_TEXT_MENTION* relationship, which records contextual metadata for each mention, enabling detailed analysis of how CCAM

concepts are discussed in the literature. The following table presents the number of nodes per entity type, together with the corresponding counts of in-text mentions.

Entity type	Number of nodes	Number of in-text mentions per source entity type
CommunicationType	5	11
SensorType	159	5,606
VehicleType	218	9,073
VRUType	24	341
LevelOfAutomation	29	69
ScenarioType	57	1,446
EntityConnectionType	32	217

Table 6: Counts of entity nodes and in-text mention relationships per entity type in the Transport-CCAM pilot graph

TRANSPORT-MARITIME PILOT GRAPH

The Transport-Maritime pilot graph extends the core graph with entities specific to maritime transport research. *VesselType* nodes represent different categories of maritime vessels, such as container ships, tankers, and offshore supply vessels, which are frequently referenced in maritime studies. These entities are connected to research products through the HAS_IN_TEXT_MENTION relationship, capturing contextual information about each occurrence. In addition, vessel types are linked to relevant Regulation entities, enabling analysis of regulatory frameworks alongside vessel-specific research. The table that follows summarises the number of *VesselType* nodes, associated in-text mentions, and regulation nodes identified in the pilot graph.

Entity type	Number of nodes	Number of in-text mentions per source entity type
VesselType	41	50,925
Regulation	22	-

Table 7: Counts of entity nodes and in-text mention relationships per entity type in the Transport-Maritime pilot graph

5. Conclusions

This deliverable presents the **final version** of the Scientific Lake service, completing the work undertaken in Work Package 2 of the SciLake project. Building upon the foundation established in D2.1, we have delivered a comprehensive data management platform that enables researchers across diverse scientific domains to efficiently discover, integrate, and analyze scientific knowledge through Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs).

5.1. Summary of Achievements

The Scientific Lake service now provides complete functionality across all four core components.

Data Acquisition and Catalogue: The PDF Aggregation Service handles acquisition of Open Access publications at scale, with distributed execution on cloud infrastructure. The data catalogue provides a central registry for all SciLake resources, enabling discovery and access across the ecosystem.

Knowledge Graph Creation Assistant: R2PG-DM enables direct mapping from relational databases to property graphs with enterprise-scale support through progressive execution, edge properties for rich relationship modeling, and PG-Schema output for standardized schemas. ProGGD provides interactive graph profiling through Graph Generating Dependencies, with the GGDMiner framework enabling automatic discovery of graph constraints and patterns.

Data Interlinking: The SHINER system implements GGD-based entity resolution, enabling identification and linking of matching entities across heterogeneous Knowledge Graphs such as the OpenAIRE Graph and domain-specific pilot graphs (Clinical Knowledge Graph, Neuroscience Knowledge Graph).

Data Lake Search and Navigation: AvantGraph provides a high-performance graph processing engine with full Cypher support. The GraphAlg algorithm language enables custom graph analytics (PageRank, shortest paths, community detection) directly within queries. Query optimization research has produced the Magellan optimizer for navigational queries and a general cardinality estimation framework for property graphs, both achieving significant performance improvements. The GraphQL-based Lake API provides standardized access for all pilots.

5.2. Research Contributions

The work described in this deliverable has resulted in significant peer-reviewed publications. The GGDMiner framework for discovering Graph Generating Dependencies was published at CIKM 2024, introducing the Answer Graph technique for scalable graph profiling [2]. The Magellan optimizer for navigational graph queries with novel seeding optimizations was published in The VLDB Journal [8]. A general cardinality estimation framework for property graph queries was published in IEEE TKDE [9]. A comprehensive treatment of GGD reasoning including satisfiability, implication, and validation was published in Information Sciences [3]. Additional work on the GraphAlg algorithm language and the GraphAlg Playground demonstration platform is currently under review.

5.3. Pilot Deployment

All pilot-specific Scientific Knowledge Graphs are now loaded and operational. The Cancer pilot integrates the Clinical Knowledge Graph with OpenAIRE cancer research publications. The Neuroscience pilot has completed EBRAINS integration and was demonstrated at FENS Forum 2024. The Energy pilot operates on the OpenAIRE dataset for energy planning containing 47M citation edges. The Transport pilot includes maritime vessel data and CCAM research publications.

The service provides the data management foundation for downstream SciLake services in WP3 (Smart Impact-driven Discovery Service) and WP4 (Smart Reproducibility Assistant Service), completing the integrated SciLake ecosystem.

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